

An improved and green synthesis of *N*-benzyl-4-formylpiperidine, a key intermediate of donepezil

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An industrially viable and green synthesis of *N*-benzyl-4-formylpiperidine (**2**), a key intermediate of *Donepezil hydrochloride* (**3**) (Aricept[®]), a selective inhibitor of acetyl cholinesterase (AChE) and the most promising agent for the treatment of mild to moderate dementia (Alzheimer). We report the synthesis of *N*-benzyl-4-formylpiperidine (**2**) by Corey-Kim oxidation of *N*-benzyl-4-hydroxymethylpiperidine (**4**) with using odorless dodecyl methyl sulfide instead of dimethyl sulfide.

Keywords: Dementia (Alzheimer), donepezil, Corey-Kim oxidation, odorless dodecyl methyl sulfide.

Introduction

Alzheimer's disease is one of the most common causes of mental deterioration of elderly people. It is characterised by degradation of various structures in the brain. Acetylcholinesterase inhibitors are the most frequently prescribed drugs for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. The Food and Drug Administration has approved donepezil for the treatment of the symptoms of Alzheimer's disease. In Alzheimer's disease, some cells in specific regions of the brain die. Because of the cell death, these brain cells lose their ability to transmit nerve impulses. Brain cells normally transmit nerve impulses by secreting various chemicals known as neurotransmitters. Brain cells that make and secrete a neurotransmitter called acetylcholine are affected early in the course of

Alzheimer's disease. Donepezil helps prevent the breakdown of acetylcholine in the brain, thus temporarily increasing its concentration. In doing so, donepezil may improve the thinking process by facilitating nerve impulse transmission within the brain. *Donepezil hydrochloride* (**3**) (Aricept[®]), a selective inhibitor of acetyl cholinesterase (AChE) and the most promising agent for the treatment of mild to moderate dementia (Alzheimer)¹ has been synthesized² by the aldol condensation of 5,6-dimethoxy-1-indanone (**1**) with *N*-benzyl-4-formylpiperidine (**2**), followed by reduction of the double bond (Scheme 1).

Several known approaches were reported to the synthesis of **2** in literature. Four of these processes start from *N*-benzyl-4-piperidone (Schemes 2–5). The first utilizes the

Scheme 1

Wittig reaction of (methoxymethyl)triphenylphosphonium chloride with *N*-benzyl-4-piperidone followed by hydrolysis of the resulting enol ether³. In another method, trimethylsilyldiazomethane is condensed with *N*-benzyl-4-piperidone followed by hydrolysis to give the final product⁴. In a third route, *N*-benzyl-4-piperidone is treated with trimethyl-oxosulfonium iodide to give the corresponding epoxide, which is then rearranged in the presence of magnesium bromide etherate to lead to **2** in high yields⁵. In 2007, a patent described the Darzens condensation of *N*-benzyl-4-piperidone with ethyl chloroacetate followed by decarboxylation².

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

Scheme 5

A fifth preparation, involves the partial reduction of *N*-benzyl-4-ethoxycarbonylpiperidine with sodium bis(2-methoxyethoxy)aluminum hydride (SMEAH) in the presence of *N*-methylpiperazine⁶ or pyrrolidine⁷ to afford compound **2** (Scheme 6). Finally, a recent procedure utilizes the Swern oxidation of **4** to furnish **2** in 73% yield after distillation⁸ (Scheme 7).

Scheme 6

Scheme 7

In our previous paper⁹, we published a more economical and efficient method (Scheme 8) for the preparation of bulk quantities of **2** from *N*-benzyl-4-hydroxypiperidine by the Corey-Kim oxidation method^{10,11}. But, here problem is commonly used dimethyl sulfide has a foul smell and unpleasant to use in laboratory. The problem becomes very worse in industry where these foul reagents are used on large scale. Odorless substitutes are required for industrial applications.

Scheme 8

Results and discussion

Recently, we have involved in process research aimed at developing odorless thiols and sulfides that can be used in organic reactions as substitutes for the usual foul-smelling thiols and sulfides^{12,13}. Among sulfides, dodecyl methyl sulfide was found to have low odorlessness for the human nose and higher boiling point than volatile dimethyl sulfide. We report a scalable, economic and green process for the large scale synthesis of *N*-benzyl-4-formylpiperidine (**2**), from *N*-benzyl-4-hydroxymethylpiperidine by the Corey-Kim oxidation method and using odorless dodecyl methyl sulfide instead of dimethyl sulfide (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9

Experimental

Solvents were dried over sodium sulfate and freshly distilled prior to use. *N*-Benzyl-4-sulfidehydroxymethylpiperidine was prepared from less expensive and commercially available ethyl isonipecotate and other chemicals including dodecyl methyl sulfide were reagent grade and available commercially. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker ADVANCE 400 MHz spectrometer, using CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as internal standard. Infrared spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 100 FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electrospray ionization mass spectroscopy was performed using an ion trap mass spectrometer (Model 6310 Agilent). Gas chromatographic analysis was performed using a Shimadzu GC-2010 Plus equipped with an Alltech poly (dimethoxysiloxane) 30 meter capillary DB-1 column.

Preparation of *N*-benzyl-4-formylpiperidine (**2**):

To a solution of *N*-benzyl-4-hydroxymethylpiperidine (61.5 g, 0.30 mol) in toluene (1200 ml) at -20°C to -40°C, dodecyl methyl sulfide (64.9 g, 0.3 mol) and triethylamine (37.2 g, 0.36 mol) were added in a single lot under argon and stirred

for 15–30 min. Then *N*-chlorosuccinimide (108 g, 0.81 mol) was added portionwise over 1 h while the internal temperature was maintained at -10°C to -15°C. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at -10°C to -15°C, completion of reaction was monitored by gas chromatography (GC). The reaction mixture was treated cautiously with aqueous sodium hydroxide (24 g in 720 ml of water) at -5°C to -10°C and then the mixture was allowed to warm to 20°C and stirred for 1 h at 20°C. The aqueous and organic layers were separated and then the aqueous layer was discarded. The organic layer was extracted with aqueous sodium bisulfite (90 g in 650 ml of water) to form the bisulfite adduct of **2**. The aqueous layer was washed with dichloromethane (40 ml) to remove impurities. The aqueous layer was then treated with aqueous sodium carbonate (25%) to adjust the pH to 9.5–9.8 and extracted with dichloromethane (400 ml). The dichloromethane extract was evaporated *in vacuo* to give the product. Distillation *in vacuo* gave **2** (51.0 g, 87.0%) as a colorless oil, b.p. 115–120°C/0.1 mm Hg, lit.⁷ 130–134°C/1 mm Hg; IR: (KBr cm⁻¹): 3027, 2922, 2804, 2760, 1723; ¹H NMR: δ 1.71 (2H, m, C-CH₂), 1.90 (2H, m, C-CH₂), 2.12 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 2.28 (1H, m, CH), 2.83–2.87 (2H, m, N-CH₂), 3.54 (2H, s, N-CH₂-Ph), 7.28 (5H, m, Ar), 9.68 (1H, d, *J* 1.2 Hz, H-C=O); MS (ESI): *m/z* 204 (M + H).

“This procedure has been scaled up using 200 g of compound **4**.”

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